

THE TEACHING OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP: A Case Study in the Area of Sciences Applied in Graduation Courses in the Interior of São Paulo

Prof. Dr. Daniela Carnio Costa Marasea, Nicole Maset Fernandes, Ingrid Carolini S. de Faria, Isadora S. da Costa Castro

Department of Business Administration of the University of Ribeirão Preto – UNAERP, Brazil

Professor of the Masters in Health and Education

Student of the Master in Health and Education

Student of Business Administration

Student of Business Administration

Abstract: Brazil is among the most entrepreneurial countries in the world and there are several programs and institutions that encourage entrepreneurship in the population. Due to the relevance of the theme, this study analyzed the incentive to entrepreneurship in higher education in the city of Ribeirão Preto, which is an educational center. This study was carried out with the investigation of undergraduate courses in the area of social sciences applied that have methodologies that encourage entrepreneurship and in the courses that have this discipline in its curricular matrix was examined how this theme was being approached in the classes. In these institutions, interviews were conducted with the coordinators of the courses, teachers and students to know the perception and effectiveness of the methodologies used, through an exploratory case study with qualitative quantitative analysis. To analyze the entrepreneurial profile of the students and the skills involved in this function, validated instruments were used to relate the results obtained. The study concluded that there are few courses that foster entrepreneurial culture, and the subject is generally approached conceptually, evidencing a deficiency in the formation of new entrepreneurs. However, one of the institutions showed in the results that its methodologies are effective and positively perceived by students.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship; University education; Teaching methodologies; Entrepreneurial culture.

I. Introduction

The field of study of entrepreneurship is an area with many researches, publications and constantly improving ideas and definitions. In the literature it is possible to find historical series that manifest distinct interpretations, that over time are lapidadas and complement each other.

The word *emprender*, *imprehendere*, comes from the medieval Latin, before the fifteenth century, and means "to try hard and difficult company", or "put into execution" (CUNHA, 2004).

Among the many meanings elaborated by other authors, in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth century, the word acquired its present meaning, first brought by Cantillon in 1775, and further improved by Say between 1815 and 1839, describing his concept of form as creating and conducting projects.

Gradually, the concept of entrepreneurship ceased to bring a vision of "business creation", and began to include risks, problem solving, ability to add value, overcome difficulties, identify opportunities and transform them, as well as the concept brought by Chiavenato (2006, p. 3): "The entrepreneur is the person who starts and / or operates a business to carry out a personal idea or project, taking risks and responsibilities and continuously innovating."

Entrepreneurship today is representative in the rise of the economy, and because of this the concern with the issue is relevant. In studies, countries such as Portugal, the United States and Canada have adopted educational policies that encourage entrepreneurship.

In Brazil, despite the great relevance of this theme, there are still few published studies that seek to know the experience about entrepreneurship education in higher education institutions. Entrepreneurship contributes not only to

economic growth but also to social development and through this, this study sought to know the stimuli and development of the future professionals of the country who are studying in the area social sciences applied.

As a research question of this project is: The undergraduate courses in Ribeirão Preto have contents aimed at teaching entrepreneurship? How effective is this teaching in the courses they have?

The general objective is to identify the courses that have contents aimed at the development of entrepreneurship in higher education institutions in Ribeirão Preto. As specific objectives, this article presents a discussion of the importance of this teaching through the graduation of undergraduate courses in the area of social sciences applied that have the discipline focused on entrepreneurship in the curricular matrix and from this, to identify the methodology worked and the existence of academic spaces for develop such skills and put into practice the concepts worked in the classroom. It was also evaluated the preparation to undertake the students who had this discipline and the perception of teachers and students about the effectiveness of the preparation received.

However, this article highlights the concepts of entrepreneurship, internal entrepreneurship, explaining how it occurs in companies, the reality of entrepreneurship education and how this process occurs, in addition to the methods proposed for this study with the presentation of results and conclusion.

II. Literature

The Entrepreneurship

The definition of entrepreneurship and its study are complex because they have different interpretations and numerous literary references. Obstacles begin in the consensus of authors, who by visions centered on their specific areas of action, attribute to the term a unique meaning, which may oppose or complement another.

Friedlaender (2004) points out that entrepreneurship has already been studied by areas of knowledge that have different perspectives, such as administration, psychology, economics, pedagogy, sociology, among others, and that due to these focused views the term has this breadth.

The author, Filion (1999), reports that entrepreneurship was first studied by economists, who tried to define the concept according to the knowledge in their discipline, and by sharing the studies with behaviorists found characteristics of human behavior expressed in the act of undertaking. For him:

The entrepreneur is a creative person, marked by the ability to establish and achieve goals and maintains a high level of awareness of the environment in which he lives, using it to detect business opportunities. An entrepreneur who continues to learn about potential business opportunities and to make moderately risky decisions aimed at innovation will continue to play an entrepreneurial role. (FILION, 1999, p.12)

He makes a survey of the main definitions of the term under discussion, as well as encompasses the scope of innovation, in which Say and Schumpeter brought in the first studies and this concept became known as one of the most complete. His summary, with essential elements, conceptualized the subject as "An entrepreneur is a person who imagines, develops and realizes visions" (FILION, 1999, p.19).

The process of innovation is inherent in entrepreneurship and can not be confused with invention, which is linked to the creation of something. The ability to innovate involves a broader concept. Thus, innovation is the ability to transform invention into a success, ie implement the new idea (PINCHOT III, 1985).

As pointed out previously in the introduction of this study, studies show that stimulating entrepreneurship in a given region or country can contribute to the development of society in different aspects. This is because the gains from investing in entrepreneurship involve not only economic ones, such as the creation of new businesses and job creation, but also social gains due to the better living conditions of society, (REDFORD 2006; DOLABELLA, 1999; ANDRADE and Torkomian, 2001; Castro and MACHADO, 2011; LOPES and TEIXEIRA, 2010) and due to so-called social enterprises (GAWELL, 2013).

In other studies such as Drucker (1986), Filion (1999), and Shumpeter (1982), benefits are seen throughout society in several aspects with the practice of entrepreneurship, such as social, cultural and technological aspects, besides the economic boom.

Entrepreneurship, according to Drucker (1986) different from what is heard in common sense, does not mean just opening a new business that aims only financial profit. The ventures can be of two types: the commercial ones, that involve investment in exchange of a profit that is expected to have; and non-commercial enterprises, such as process improvement, social projects, education, health services, among others. For him, enterprises aim at an income, which can be expressed as the concept of profit, or as something non-monetary but that adds value, as an improvement in the income of education, health, an activity, service or process, etc.

Some authors, such as Gawell (2013), defend the distinction of the social enterprise from the commercial, where the social is developed for philanthropic reasons and the identification of opportunities occurs from a lack in society.

The GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor) is a worldwide research program, founded in 1999, and aims to deepen knowledge on issues related to entrepreneurship worldwide (INSTITUTO BRASILEIRO DE QUALIDADE E PRODUTIVIDADE, 2011). According to this body, entrepreneurship can be identified in two ways with regard to motivation, that is, the conditions of the environment in which the individual lives that have boosted the entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurship can occur due to the opportunity or need of the individuals or groups, as they do not have, for example, better financial conditions or work options. Therefore, the interesting thing is that the countries can reduce the rates of entrepreneurship caused by necessity and increase entrepreneurship by opportunity, since the latter reveals better social and economic conditions of society.

Other authors defend different views on the one made by the GEM, such as Dantas (2011), which adds inertial entrepreneurship, which is generally represented by the passage of a stick from father to son or by affinity in relationships, which is independent of the entrepreneurial capacity to make it happen.

According to the GEM survey in 2016, 75% of the nascent entrepreneurs are seeking entrepreneurship by opportunity, and the proportion of 57.4% for new businesses based on this type.

The motivations that make a person an entrepreneur, are linked to multiple factors, which may be internal or external to him, ie, social, economic, environmental, personal characteristics, or several of these influencing the entrepreneur together potential. (DORNELAS, 2008).

Characteristics such as liking responsibility, not liking repetitive and routine work, high energy, high perseverance, strong imagination, and willingness to take calculated and planned risks are also characteristics that make up an entrepreneurial profile according to Birley and Muzyka (2001).

Dantas (2011) also emphasizes the achievement and need for professional or personal ascension as the motivation above any other. He explains that the enterprise, in most cases, becomes the main objective of the individual, and becomes an extension of himself. The success of the venture is thus related to the success of the entrepreneur, who in turn, wants the rise of the enterprise, representing his desire for personal or professional ascension.

According to the different lines of definitions, in a broader way, entrepreneurship can be defined as the act of identifying an opportunity, idealizing actions, and realizing them in an innovative way, adding values not necessarily financial to society. It is not only linked to the opening of companies, as it can be linked to any innovation related to a product, service, process improvements, troubleshooting, among others.

Internal Entrepreneurship

Internal entrepreneurship is also known as intrapreneurship or corporate entrepreneurship, which generally defines a set of actions that encourage the employee of a company to think like owner, that is, to have a vision of owner within the organization to which it is a part, within the concept seen, to undertake in its function.

The term Internal Entrepreneurship or Intrapreneurship was first used around 1978 with Gifford Pinchot III, referring to the entrepreneurial action that takes place within an already existing organization. The intrapreneur for him would be one who uses his creativity and talent to conduct entrepreneurial projects within an organization to which he belongs (ESTEVAM, 2012).

Since the 1980s, large companies such as GE, 3M, Volvo, The Economist, and Texas Instruments, among others, have already taken the entrepreneurship incentive stance in their employees (PINCHOT III, 1985; DORNELAS 2003).

With the dynamism of the market the internal entrepreneurship was being valued and research in this line of thought arose. For Dantas (2011), internal entrepreneurship can occur. Companies need to encourage this in their employees through their organizational policies and practices, developing an environment conducive for the employee to innovate and execute their ideas. This can be stimulated through professional recognition, the granting of greater autonomy within the work process, awards, among other strategies.

Drucker (1986) argues that organizational culture stimulates the entrepreneurial spirit within the work, encourages its employees to always seek innovation, be it a product, the best way to develop something or perfect a process, which leads the employee to have greater dedication and commitment to the work developed in the company.

Internal entrepreneurship shows that someone can achieve professional fulfillment even if they are employees and not having their own business. Moreover, authors such as Pinchott (1985) add that this kind of entrepreneurship can be momentary or occasional, not necessarily following a behavioral profile at all times. For this author, internal entrepreneurs are visionists, for they foresee the possible barriers and direct their actions thinking of deviating from them, which he called "dreaming with open eyes."

Dornelas (2003, p.59) states that "people want to be recognized and admired ... they want to leave a legacy", and preaches that the company that knows how to use this personal internal motivation, is able to develop great intrapreneurs.

In several studies teamwork appears in the definitions of this type of entrepreneurship. A negative point is that in trying to promote entrepreneurial behavior, if strategies are not well structured, they can stimulate competition and excessive competition among employees, which can certainly shake the team.

With the current difficulties and strong competition in the market, internal entrepreneurship is part of the "reinventing" of companies. For this reason it has grown and is part of the requirements of human resources professionals in the selection of candidates.

Entrepreneurial Education Process

The process of entrepreneurial education is the teaching of entrepreneurship, which according to Lopes (2010), can not be passed only as theory, since it involves the development and learning of knowledge, skills, attitudes and qualities. Therefore, their approach must be different from traditional ones, using "learning by doing" methodologies, which force students to think of exits and alternatives, learning from their own experience.

In this line of thinking, many authors defend the entrepreneurial pedagogy, which is a methodology of entrepreneurship focused on basic education, which reaches children up to high school. One of the authors who discusses the subject is Dolabela (2003), who believes that it is an alternative to establish a future entrepreneurial culture, where the construction of knowledge is joint and not only based on the transfer of knowledge. However, he emphasizes that before implanting entrepreneurial pedagogy it is necessary to create a typical Brazilian entrepreneurial culture, taking into account the peculiarities of the country, which in turn uses models imported from other countries.

Lopes (2010) supports this idea and adds that the objectives of learning change with age and that the great challenge for adults is to deconstruct experiences of their training and culture, which imprisons them in certain behaviors and abilities. In this way, one should focus on the personal skills related to entrepreneurship from the schools and maintained until the higher education.

Investing in entrepreneurial education can be found in the world a few years ago, as is the case in Germany, the United Kingdom, Finland, France, the United States and Canada. In Africa, specifically in Mozambique, it was possible to find an experience of applying a curricular model in professional schools, and among the results found were the achieved goal of developing attitudes and entrepreneurial behaviors in the students, and in the medium term it was already possible to identify an improvement socioeconomic level of the community where the experience was carried out (CASTRO and MACHADO, 2011).

Based on the assumption that it is possible to develop the entrepreneurial profile in individuals, and against the idea that to be an entrepreneur it is necessary to be born with different personality traits, many companies and universities invest in development, training and disciplines who discuss entrepreneurship, trying to encourage this practice. (SANTOS, CAETANO and CURRAL 2010).

Brazil is among the five most entrepreneurial countries in the world and many research on this subject has been boosted and developed, as well as debates and investments in the entrepreneurial culture. The creation of institutions such as the Sebrae in 1972 and other bodies encouraged the development of enterprises and encouraged the opening of small and medium businesses. Incubators were created in the 1980s, and in the 1990s more investment was made in training programs and training for entrepreneurs.

The State University of Campinas (Unicamp) is one of the Brazilian universities that promote the entrepreneurial culture from an early age in the students. In addition to being one of the largest sources of research in the world, it also raises the importance of the presence of junior companies in the university environment for the promotion of entrepreneurship, where they allow students to take risks that are first supported by a responsible teacher, to take risks of projects alone.

Andrade and Torkomian (2001) emphasize the importance of university faculty to encourage entrepreneurship education not only in a particular subject, but also throughout the courses relating the subject to other subjects.

Therefore, the incentive to entrepreneurial education is one of the paths towards economic and social growth and development. In Brazil, the stimulus can still be considered small or flawed, since according to Sebrae data, 25% and 50% of small and medium-sized companies closed their activities less than two and five years respectively, despite the efforts of the institutions against this movement. Little is known how these stimuli have been done, since there are few studies that present experiences and results in the country, a fact that stimulated interest in the theme of this work.

III. Methods

The development of this work was carried out in two parts, the first one of primary and secondary data collection referring to the discipline of entrepreneurship, addressing the colleges courses that offered this course and a second part that elaborated a case study.

According to Yin (2005) the case study is an empirical investigation on a certain subject inserted in a certain reality, being necessary for so much that there is planning for this study, techniques of data collection and analysis of the same. It is a study that is at once unique, focused on the object (case) and multiple insofar as the methods can be replicated by other researchers of this object in other contexts.

In order to expand the field research, an exploratory case study was used, where the research seeks to formulate questions or a problem, "... with threefold purpose: to develop hypotheses, to increase the familiarity of the researcher with an environment, fact or phenomenon to carry out more precise future research or to modify and clarify concepts "(MARCONI LAKATOS, 2008 p.85).

Ribeirão Preto was chosen for two reasons: this city is considered as an educational center, counting with 10 universities, besides the postgraduate courses and also for the development that is in the center of the region referring to the diversification of the economy and quality of life, according to data from the City of Ribeirão Preto. Nevertheless, more than 80 municipalities are part of the region, reaching 03 million inhabitants with a per capita income equivalent to two times the Brazilian average. The region has an incentive from the City Hall of Ribeirão Preto, SEBRAE, SINCOVARP and Casa do Contabilista providing care to people who pretend to be entrepreneurs, called "entrepreneur's room", due to the contribution that the city is developing with entrepreneurship. (MUNICIPAL COUNCIL OF RIBEIRÃO PRETO, 2013)

In relation to the population and sample the type of sampling was intentional, as defined by Marconi and Lakatos (2008). Intentional sampling is the one that the researcher is interested in the information of certain elements of the population. The researcher does not address the "mass" of the population, but rather those that are judged appropriate within a specific context.

For this part of the research was carried out the secondary data survey, focusing on the courses that provided the curriculum matrix on the internet, among them were the undergraduate courses of the Institutions of Education of Ribeirão Preto that had the discipline of entrepreneurship.

In order to obtain a more effective result of the sample, public schools in the city of Ribeirão Preto were withdrawn, since the context of public and private education has specific characteristics.

The research was carried out in 02 Institutions of Higher Education (with the authorization term - TCLE), where it was investigated which courses had the discipline of entrepreneurship, in this survey there were 03 courses, being Administration at University 01, Administration at University 02 and Accounting Sciences (these denominations were created to maintain the confidentiality of the institutions that participated).

The coordinators of the selected courses were interviewed individually and the same procedure occurred with the professors who ministered the discipline of entrepreneurship.

The sample collection of this research was attended by the coordinator and professor of U1, coordinator and professor of U2 and coordinator and professor of Accounting Sciences. The coordinators of the Administration course U1 and U2 carry out more than one function in the course or work in more than one course, as well as the course teacher Administration U.2. The representation in table 1 follows.

Table 1: List of teachers and coordinators interviewed

PROFESSOR	COORDINATOR	COURSE
AdministrationU.1	X	X
Administration U.2	X	X
Accounting Sciences	X	X

Source: Prepared by the authors

The data collection took place in two parts, being carried out in the Institutions of Higher Education that accepted to participate in this research, after the proper authorizations of the coordinators, teachers and students. All participants signed the Free and Informed Consent Form (TCLE), where they agreed to participate in the research.

The first stage happened with the course coordinators and teachers who were within the parameter of integration of the population sample, the interviews were based on the dimensions explained below in table 2. In the second stage the students were also included in the mentioned parameters in the first step. Data collection was done through individual structured interviews and the application of the protocol on the entrepreneurial profile of Dornelas (2003), namely "Self-evaluation of the Entrepreneurial Profile", "Self-Assessment of Entrepreneurial Skills" and "Personal Questionnaire", the aim of this study was to evaluate the preparation and reception of the content of entrepreneurship.

The interview is a professional meeting between two people, with the purpose of obtaining information on the part of the researcher about a certain subject. It is a data technique widely used in social research and is considered as excellent

for obtaining data, when done by a good researcher who takes the necessary care. (MARCONI LAKATOS 2008). (GIL 1999, p. 117) complements the data collection technique [...] The interview is quite adequate to obtain information about what people know, believe, expect, feel or desire, they intend to do, do or did.

After the data collection the next step was to interpret them, considering the investigation of the possible relations between the phenomenon studied and factors analyzed.

The interviews were carried out with 02 coordinators in a single block due to the correlation between them.

The dimensions of the elements found in the interviews are shown in Table 2 and the sums of the notes corresponding to the description of the degree of entrepreneurship are shown in Table 3.

Table 2: Dimensions categorized from interviews

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DIMENSIONS	
1. Course Structure	Elements related to the actual structure of the undergraduate course related to the teaching of entrepreneurship, such as information about the subjects, pedagogical project of the course, workload, etc.
2. Importance of Entrepreneurial Education for the course	The elements corresponding to what the interviewees think about the importance of entrepreneurship teaching specifically within the undergraduate course they coordinate or teach have been gathered in this dimension.
3. Importance of Entrepreneurial Education in undergraduate	The classification of this dimension was based on the opinion of the interviewees regarding the importance of teaching entrepreneurship in undergraduate courses in general, as a possible practice of any institution of higher education.
4. Brazilian Reality	The category that brings the elements related to the Brazilian scenario on entrepreneurship, both in question in the current economic context, and the reality found in entrepreneurship education
5. Teaching methodologies used	In this dimension were categorized elements that concern the teaching strategies and contents worked in the subjects of entrepreneurship of the courses investigated
6. Results of the Entrepreneurial Education provided	Elements that indicate the results obtained by the students, after the entrepreneurial education received were allocated in this dimension.
7. Difficulties encountered	This category gathers the complaints of difficulties encountered in the field of entrepreneurship. As in dimension number 4, the difficulties encountered refer to both the entrepreneurial act itself and the teaching discussed in the interviews.
8. Pretensions of change for the course	The elements that pointed to the will or need for change, or even new plans to be implemented in the surveyed undergraduate courses, were allocated in this dimension.

9. Pretensions of change for entrepreneurship as a whole	Elements referring to the ambitions that the interviewees have regarding the changes of entrepreneurship in a general way, looking at society in a general way.
--	---

Source: Dornelas (2003)

In order to analyze the entrepreneurial profile, the protocol of Dornelas (2003) was used, the sums of the notes correspond to the description of the degree of entrepreneurship, as shown in the table below:

Table 3: Analysis of the Entrepreneurial Profile of Dornelas (2003)

SCORE	DESCRIPTION OF THE NOTE
120 to 150	You are of course already an entrepreneur, because it has entrepreneurial characteristics, being therefore prone to stand out in the company.
90 to 119	You have several characteristics of entrepreneur, can even act as such, however need to balance the strengths and weaknesses.
60 to 89	You are not very entrepreneurial at the moment and possibly handle yourself as a traditional administrator most of the time. To make a difference, you will have to practice entrepreneurial attitudes and analyze the main weaknesses.
Less than 59	You are not an entrepreneur and if you continue to do so you will rarely be one. Certainly prefer to continue to be followed. (That does not mean it does not have qualities). If the career in the company requires a more entrepreneurial profile, rectify your professional life and your goals.

Source: Dornelas (2003, pp. 80 and 83)

In the quantitative data, we used the analysis guide belonging to the instrument already validated developed by Dornelas (2003, page 80 and page 83) and the technique of simple descriptive statistics, where the weights of the scores were according to the self-assessment performed by the interviewees.

IV. Results And Discussion Of Data

When analyzing the collected data, it was observed that the entrepreneurial education is still little worked, and when it is worked, it is limited to the courses directed to the management area. Ferreira (2003) says that entrepreneurship education in Brazil has a very small scope and is mostly focused in the area of Exact or in the Administration area, since the entrepreneurial activity still appears related only with the opening of new companies. Costa (2011) points out that the Brazilian context of not stimulating a typical entrepreneurial culture of the country, through political incentives and Entrepreneurial Education, contributes greatly to the disinformation of the population about entrepreneurship and consequently not to identify the importance of this activity.

The data analysis was performed in 9 Dimensions, which are:

- Dimension 01 - Course Structure:

The disciplines directed to entrepreneurship are divided differently by semesters. Being: 50% at the beginning of the training (Administration U2 and Accounting Sciences) and 50% more towards the end of the course. (Administration U1) Even with these numbers, the course coordinators affirm that entrepreneurship is seen as an integrated project of the courses, in this way the subject of entrepreneurship is also approached in other disciplines or other projects that occur during the course developing the teaching of the entrepreneurship. As can be identified in the lines:

"I would say that 60% to 70% of the course subjects in a direct or indirect way, contribute to entrepreneurial actions" (R.D.);

"[...] we have this goal from the beginning, practically in all disciplines" (L.L.P).

Continuing in this dimension, appear the Juniores companies used as a stage of stimulation for the students to undertake, 90% of the interviewed aim at the space of the Junior company as good for the promotion of entrepreneurship, walking the same way as Ferreira and Mattos (2003) and Jorge, Lotufo and Cortez (2007) that cite experiences in other Brazilian Universities that achieve positive results of entrepreneurship with the work of the companies Juniores. In this way this space provides the ability of students to take risks, considering the reality that exists in the market. According to the authors these experiences develop entrepreneurial skills to undertake such as creativity and innovation.

• In Dimensions 02 and 03 - Importance of Entrepreneurial Education and Importance of Entrepreneurial Education in Graduation:

The coordinators and professors interviewed affirm the importance of teaching entrepreneurship, both in undergraduate and higher education in general. As some examples cited:

"I think it is very important from the point of view of learning, from the point of view of vocational training ... and even from the point of view of people improving society" (R.D.);

"[...] I believe that it is fundamental nowadays that we develop the competence to undertake" (J.E.F);

"I think it's fantastic" (K.L.F.A).

As previously mentioned, Duker (1986), Fillion (1999) and Shumpeter (1982) have identified a few years ago that the development of entrepreneurial actions would influence the economic progress and social well-being of the population, confirming the emphasis shown by the coordinators and teachers in relation to the importance of entrepreneurship education.

• Dimension 04 - Brazilian Reality:

Notifies the economic scenario of the country that does not stimulate entrepreneurship, 60% of respondents affirm this lack. This data can be considered very important, since no specific questions were asked regarding the reality of Brazil in entrepreneurship. In this case how much the country's laws prevent people from undertaking as they would like. Below are the complaints made by the interviewees:

"[...] It is difficult to undertake especially in a country such as Brazil where it has a tax, such a large tax burden" (J.E.F);

"[...] We have an aggravation of finding difficulties of openings of companies [...]. How do I want to enrich my society and put obstacles of this nature? "

(R.A.L);

"[...] It seems that the system, he does not want to be undertaken, has already become a machine that fights against the entrepreneur" (M.A.M)

• Dimension 05 - Teaching Methodologies Used:

On this category there is once again the unanimity in the development of a business plan of the discipline and also on the mixtures of strategies of the traditional model of teaching with the active models of teaching and learning. Teachers indicate the need to use the blackboard in the discipline discipline to work on certain concepts, however in some moments are essential to employ the active methodologies in order to achieve the development of entrepreneur profile in students.

The strategies mentioned are: case studies, group dynamics, debates, exercises based on real news about entrepreneurship and also problem-based learning known as PBL. Approximately 71.4% of the professors said to raise the practices of the entrepreneurial profile at the beginning of the course, with an intent to know and develop the skills and also identify the students who have more proximity to this profile.

Among the mentioned methodological strategies, there is a highlight in the U1 Administration, with a project called "Gourmet Fair". This planning is part of an integrated project that takes place in the last stage of the course, involving all disciplines and the challenge is to design a company on paper and put it into practice, with all risks and benefits, including financial.

In the administration of U1, students begin to participate in projects integrated in the third stage, where the projects function as a consultant in order to make diagnoses and put into practice the proposals based on the disciplines that are participating in the integrated project. The students really go to the market, they take on the role of junior consultants, in this case there is a teacher accompanying and assisting the whole process. In the sixth stage it is the moment for the students to also dedicate themselves to the TCC, so the activities provided by the Junior company are extended to all

students, even if there are those who did not participate in the Junior company, the "peculiarities" of entrepreneurship are met.

Another strategy acquired by the Administration U.2 is an integrated project during the course, starting in the third stage until reaching the TCC. The intention is to make the profile of the entrepreneur be "instigated" in the student and developed throughout the project, aiming to achieve a business plan. The course coordinator said he was surprised at the level of presentation of the students, for the interest and commitment shown.

The explanations given by the interviewees were to the question of the importance that the practice brings to the students, in relation to the skills and capacities that can be developed and expanded through such action (practice), besides these teaching methodologies allow the contact with the reality of fact. According to the examples:

"The theory is very important [...] you experience a practice without the theory does not help, because you will be vague [...] we have different methods for each situation" (R.A.L);

"I particularly work with two methodologies; a traditional and a more behavioral, making the student more agent in his teaching and learning process" (J.E.F).

There is agreement between the interviewees' reports and the literature, the teaching of entrepreneurship related to the attitudes and behaviors that can therefore be developed in the students (LOPES2010). The teacher understands that:

"[...] does not mean that they (the people) were born more creative than the others. Some had more situations that caused them to further develop this activity [...]" (K.L.F.A);

"Because it does not matter, I believe you do not reach a discipline like this and present a business plan, not to mention the importance of developing some behaviors" (J.E.F).

In Entrepreneurial Education, active teaching methodologies must be explored, since they allow the student to "learn by doing" (LOPES, P 29,2010). In this way, when faced with practice, the individual is exposed to think, which contributes to the development of entrepreneurial profile skills. The Entrepreneurial Education suggested by some researchers of the area should then take into account that the practice and the experiences are more important than the content at that moment (LOPES, 2010)

Dimension 06 - Results of Entrepreneurial Education:

The coordinators and teachers believe that 60% of the students took up after the course, this result is seen as positive by them (teachers and coordinators). Already 40% believe that this result is very small. However in recent years, have had students in the assessed city who have opened successful businesses. As for example the U1 Administration course part of the students used the business plan to undertake (In the last 05 years 02 coffee shops, 01 premium products shop, were assembled in malls in the city of Ribeirão Preto and 01 light food store) .

In contrast, the courses denounce a low result considering factors such as:

A. The fact that the entrepreneurial culture is far from the reality of the country, influences the lack of stimulation.

B. The development of intrapreneurship can contribute to these results, since the fact that the student is stimulated in the school to undertake does not mean that he needs to open some kind of business, on the contrary he can act as such in the company that is to work (as an entrepreneur)

• Dimension 07- Difficulties Found:

60% of the people interviewed say that the difficulties encountered are those mentioned in the "Dimension 04 Brazilian Reality" being: Taxes, taxes and etc., in general the things that prevent entrepreneurship from happening fully, (without barriers) and the fact that country does not have an entrepreneurial culture. How was said:

"[...] Bill Gates and Stevie Jobs [...] they did not study entrepreneurship from the University, they simply took it there (in the US) it's part of a culture [...] Now here in Brazil due to a whole failure of this culture [...] is a struggle every day" (MAM)

In the USA, for example, this entrepreneurial culture is stimulated by entrepreneurship disciplines since high school, because, regardless of their future professional field, there is previously a concern for individuals to undertake and for the entrepreneurial culture to continue (LOPES, 2010).

Dornelas (2003, p.15) brings culture as a "collective programming of the mind, typical of a social group," and in this thought builds the idea of entrepreneurial culture, directly influencing the attitudes and behaviors of individuals who share this culture.

This can be felt in the educational scope of the undergraduate courses that were surveyed.

- Dimension 08 - Pretension of Change for the Course:

30% of respondents are awaiting change in results in entrepreneurship education:

"... I would like to see something more consistent [...] although I can form an egress with entrepreneurial capacity, not necessarily he becomes an entrepreneur" (A.C.P.J)

Already 10% of the interviewees want to see changes in the interest of students in relation to entrepreneurship. Still 60% want changes in the projects of the courses, where 40% of these are aimed at the creation of Junior companies for the undergraduate course. On the other hand, 30% is aimed at increasing the number of hours to discuss entrepreneurship during the course, also aiming at the creation of new spaces, integrating universities, investors and society, in order to enable a greater "exchange" between them.

- Dimension 09 - Pretension of Change for Entrepreneurship as a whole:

There were identified 04 aspects for change, being:

- a. Change of entrepreneurship, aiming at the progress of social welfare, in order to form a more just society, and can be provided by local economic development.
- b. Maturity in relation to the entrepreneurial activities, being thought, planned and decided with transparency. Leaving entrepreneurship out of necessity, since most people who "choose" this type of entrepreneurship are not prepared, which directly reflects the mortality of companies in the market.
- c. Incentive in the country's entrepreneurial culture, with lower taxes and taxes and more educational and governmental stimulus for society as a whole.
- d. To better explore the opportunities of the new global business chains, since this type of exploration is carried out by other countries.

Results And Comparative Tables

In the first semesters the subjects related to entrepreneurship are taught at U2. Administration and Accounting Sciences, already in U1. Appear closer to the end of the course.

In 71.4% of the teachers, the practice of raising the profile of the students at the beginning of the course not only to discover the skills that need to be more developed, but also to identify if the student has the most entrepreneurial or intrapreneur profile. The courses that have this practice are: Administration U.2 and Accounting Sciences.

In all analyzed courses, 100% of students who participated in the interviews said they recognize the goal of developing the entrepreneurial profile along the degree course, and the students of U1's management and directors of U2 chose the institutions entrepreneurship, with 15.38% and 20%, respectively. In the course of Accounting Sciences, 80% of the students reported having chosen the institution without knowing the existence of this objective.

About the commitment and dedication in the specific disciplines offered on entrepreneurship, U1's Administration course students, in their majority, classified themselves as "Good", with 46.15% of the cases, followed by 38.47% as "Very Good" and 15.38% as "Excellent". The U2 Administration course indicates a median dedication to this subject and the Accounting Sciences course was 60% with a "Good" performance, 20% with "Very Good" and 20% as "Excellent" performance.

With regard to the spaces destined to the development of entrepreneurial abilities, the students affirm in the great majority to ignore projects or spaces in the faculty that have this type of incentive, presenting the following data:

- Administration U1 - 70% do not recognize or do not attend spaces for this type of improvement, against 30% who claim to participate in other spaces (such as Junior Company and / or Gourmet Fair), events, lectures and extracurricular courses;
- U2 Administration - 90% of the students say they did not participate in any other area beyond the disciplines provided in the teaching schedule, compared to 10% who participated in the Administration Week;
- Accounting Sciences - 60% said they had not attended any other space outside the discipline, compared to 40% who cited Lectures as other spaces attended.

In general, the students interviewed believe that these incentives are important within universities. The U1 Administration course was the only one in which there was formalized another space for developing entrepreneurship

as the Junior Company. However, not relevant representative of this company on the data collected is probably linked the extent that the company has in college, as inside work around 20 students, this number does not represent 0.5% of the students enrolled in the Management U1.

It is possible to analyze separately each question evaluated and its variables. In this way, the following comparative tables follow the data analysis:

Table 4: Students' opinions with the teaching methodologies used in the course

VARIABLES	U1. ADMINISTRATION	U2. ADMINISTRATION	ACCOUNTING SCIENCES
Excellent	7.69%	0%	0%
Very Good	76.72%	80%	80%
Good	15.59%	20%	20%

Source: prepared by the authors

It is noticeable that the U1 Administration course has the best methodologies in the opinion of the students, responsible for approximately 85% when adding the variables "Excellent" and "Very Good", being the only one to present results in the "Excellent" category. A smaller percentage in comparison to the other courses affirm in this same institution that the methodology is only "Good", that is, satisfactory in comparison to the minimum that the students expect.

Table 5: The evaluation of students' interest in the development of the entrepreneurial profile

VARIABLES	U1. ADMINISTRATION	U2. ADMINISTRATION	ACCOUNTING SCIENCES
Excellent	46.15%	0%	0%
Very Good	46.15%	30%	60%
Good	7.7%	70%	40%

Source: prepared by the authors

It is noted that the students of the U1 Administration course have a greater interest in the development of the entrepreneurial profile. It is possible to verify that this data maintains the course in the first place because in it there is a greater penetration on the subject of entrepreneurship, therefore, the students are encouraged to develop due to the knowledge acquired in the classes and through the methodologies used in this institution.

Table 6: Students' perception of the readiness to undertake

VARIABLES	U1. ADMINISTRATION	U2. ADMINISTRATION	ACCOUNTING SCIENCES
Prepared	76.92%	40%	60%
Reasonably prepared	23.08%	60%	20%
Do not feel prepared	0%	0%	20%

Source: prepared by the authors

Regarding the students' perception in the preparation provided by the institution, the data show that the situation of the Accounting Sciences course is more critical, in which 20% do not feel prepared. This data represents a point to be improved, since it was the only course to opt for this variable. However, this is a tangible action, since the students who feel prepared are part of the majority of the interviewees and in this variable the course is open to the U2 Administration.

Table 7: Responses to the questionnaire 2 - Self-assessment of the entrepreneurial profile

ENTREPRENEUR PROFILE	U1. ADMINISTRATION	U2. ADMINISTRATION	ACCOUNTING SCIENCES
Level 4	15.39%	30%	80%
Level 3	76.92%	60%	20%
Level 2	7,69%	10%	0%

Source: prepared by the authors

The responses to questionnaire 2 resulted in the data presented above. Level 4 of the entrepreneurial profile is the most advanced, and we realize that at this level the course of Administration of U1 is behind the other courses. It is noteworthy that the results obtained in the Accounting Sciences class may have been influenced by two questionnaires that presented equal answers, to which they could not be invalidated and their data were considered in the sample. Therefore, it is possible to analyze that the greatest results were found in levels 3 and 4, that is, the students show strong abilities to undertake and when allied to the incentive in the classrooms can become entrepreneurs of the types that were cited in this article.

Regarding questionnaire 3, "Self-evaluation of entrepreneurial skills", the following skills were analyzed.

Table 8: Entrepreneurial skills assessed

1.Motivation for achievement:A desire to make happen, to achieve a high standard of achievement / achievement of goals.
2.Self-control (of destiny):Feeling of influencing the course of events in your life. Destiny is defined more by something internal of the person than due to extreme factors.
3.Propensity to take risks:Take calculated risks and seek information before you act. Desire to be responsible for actions.
4.Troubleshooting:Someone who knows how to solve problems of forming realistic and touches an operation / business without needing much help from others.
5.Influencer: He who finds people who help him meet his own goals. He knows how to persuade people to work toward a goal he sets.

Source: prepared by the authors based on the feedback of the instrument used.

In this questionnaire it was observed that the students of the Administration course of U1 perceive a deficiency in relation to the ability to be an influencer, where 100% of the sample presented below average marks. Regarding the development of risk-taking and problem-solving abilities, the marks achieved were the same for both items, 38.6% below average, 38.46% with medium marks, and 23.07% with skills developed above of the average. In self-control, 53.8% also did not reach the average grade for this skill, 38.4% reached the middle category, and only 7.6% received above-average grade. The last evaluated skill to be commented on is the motivation for achievement, the only one in which the majority of the students reached above average scores, being represented by 38.4% against 30.8% with average grades and 30.8% with grades below of the average.

As can be seen, the students, although they have developed the entrepreneurial profile, when they make a self-assessment about their abilities in relation to the indicators necessary to undertake better, point out the ability to be influential as the skill that needs to be the most worked. It is worth mentioning that this ability does not involve the activity of undertaking by itself, it implies in fact that the entrepreneur influences others and persuades them to achieve a goal stipulated by him. This influential item presupposes the development of leadership skills as an employer, a

characteristic that is not necessarily worked out by the curricular matrix of the course, while teaching entrepreneurial skills. The skills developed by the methodologies used in the course focus much more on individual entrepreneurship, on the development of characteristics such as teamwork and proactivity.

The second skill that most needs to be worked, pointed by the students was the one of self-control, this ability refers to the sensation of influencing the events of life, that is, a control over the external factors and destiny. The perception that they can not have complete control over the events of their life, demonstrate a certain maturity and close perception of the reality of what happens in the dynamic labor market, such as the Brazilian market. Although the instrument suggests a great need for self-control, it is believed that this need is met by the average indicators in the items problem solving, risk-taking propensity and motivation for achievement. Thus, it is confirmed in the author's view of this work and based on the data presented here that the Administration U.1 course promotes and develops the entrepreneurial profile.

In the U2 Administration course students indicated lower scores also related to influencing ability - 90% below average, and 10% with average grade - and self-control ability, which did not score above average, with 40% on average and 60% below average for the development of this skill. The grades on achievement motivation ability again appear to be the hardest hit, with 70% of students above average and 30% of students achieving median grades. Prone to risk-taking skills and problem solving, most students score below average, being 60% and 50% respectively, and both characteristics with 30% of above-average grades.

In this course there is a greater concern regarding the need to develop the entrepreneurial skills evaluated, since the perception of the students points to a results that are mostly below the average in four of the five skills that have been raised, namely self-control, propensity to take risks, problem solving and influencer. The only ability in which most students scored above average was the motivation for achievement.

What can be taken from this is the expression of a slightly distorted perception about the market reality versus the preparation of the same ones to be undertaken, considering the entrepreneurial profile, once in answering the questionnaire 2, the students gave more notes. However, when responding to questionnaire 3, in which the skills are evaluated through the expression of behaviors, it was evident the lack of development of the same. This fact ends up being a consequence of the methodologies of promotion to the entrepreneurship used by the course, since they have a more theoretical character in terms of transmission of knowledge and fundamentals necessary to undertake it, than the entrepreneurial activity itself. As described by a student:

"The classes are very good, but I miss having more experience, work here in the university closer to the reality of what we will find in our day to day work ..."

In addition, one can also consider as indicative of this methodology more theoretical than practical, the teacher's talk about the Business Fair developed:

"... there were exactly 39 groups, 39 business models, they brought business experimentation, and it was supposed to be just slide presentation ..." (L.L.P.)

Ultimately, although it is possible to find in the Administration course of U.2., Reporting on the use of active teaching and learning methodologies, the focus of this teaching is not the development of the skills needed for entrepreneurial activity, and in fact the results found relates to a knowledge of the theory and fundamentals of entrepreneurship as a concept and as an activity in the job market.

Risk-prone and problem-solving skills are above average for most students in the Accounting Science course, with 80% and 60% of respondents respectively. The self-control and influencing characteristics are below average in most students, needing to be more developed in 60% of students both skills. The motivation for achievement appears tied with 40% of students achieving median grades and 40% with grades above on average for this skill.

In relation to teaching in the course of Accounting Sciences, which is done by the same professor of the course of Administration of U2, one can see a methodology more focused on the foundations of the enterprise than of the development of the entrepreneurial capacities. In this case, students observe that at the end of the course some concepts have already been lost and comparing the motivation to undertake, analyzed previously, explains why they feel unmotivated, once they know the subject superficially and practice is not encouraged.

All other courses analyzed until then had the motivation ability to perform with most of the above average scores, but in the course of Accounting Sciences this characteristic was rated below average. It is suggested that the motives of this result be investigated, since the motivation for achievement is related to the desire to make something happen, to

achieve a high standard of achievement of its goals, and therefore, is a driving force of entrepreneurship, and the lack of it can be seen as a disincentive. The factors related to this result may be internal to the course or to the educational institution, as can be external, related for example with the current scenario of entrepreneurship in Brazil, or with the life experiences of these students.

V. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

According to data obtained during the course of the research, it was identified that only one of the analyzed universities effectively develops the teaching of entrepreneurship, being the Administration course of U.1.

The methodologies used in this course correspond to the practices developed during the course, providing more autonomy in the students' learning. One of the purposes offered in the course is the development of the entrepreneurial profile, where the main objective is to put the student in contact with the reality through the entrepreneurial activities, with intent to expand the abilities. Making theory and practice go hand in hand.

In the courses of Administration of U.2 and Accounting Sciences the development of practical entrepreneurship was not so effective, considering that the teaching methods are more directed to the theory.

After collecting data and information on this research, it was possible to reveal the importance of stimulating entrepreneurship, not only in the educational, but also in the social, professional and cultural spheres.

For future research there are suggestions regarding the exploration of other courses, addressing the different types of efficient methodologies that can be used in each of them, making the students have more incentive and at the same time feel comfortable to deal with this theme, aiming at the full development of the entrepreneurial profile,

The final result of this study allows a more detailed analysis of the new paths that can be traced by coordinators and teachers, based on seeking greater flexibility and effectiveness in entrepreneurship education in general.

REFERENCES

- 1) ANDRADE, Renato Fonseca; TORKOMIAN, Ana Lucia Vitale. *Fatores de influência na estruturação de programas de educação empreendedora em instituições de ensino superior*. In: Encontro de Estudos Sobre Empreendedorismo e Gestão de Pequenas Empresas, 2001. Anais... Londrina, PR, II EGEPE, p. 299-311. 2001.
- 2) AUSTIN, James; STEVENSON, Howard; WEI-SKILLERN, Jane. *Social and comercial entrepreneurship: same, different, or both?* Revista de Administração, São Paulo, v.47, n.3, p.370-384, julho-setembro. 2012.
- 3) BARDIN, Laurence. *Análise de Conteúdo*. Lisboa: Edições 70, 2004.
- 4) BIRLEY, Sue; MUZYKA, Daniel K. *Dominando os desafios do empreendedor*. São Paulo: MakronBooksLtda, 2001.
- 5) BULGACOV, Yara Lúcia M. ET AL. *Jovem empreendedor no Brasil: a busca do espaço da realização ou a fulga da exclusão?* Revista de Administração Pública, Rio de Janeiro, v.45, n.3, p.695-720, maio-junho. 2011.
- 6) CHIAVENATO, Idalberto. *Empreendedorismo: dando asas ao espírito empreendedor*. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2006.
- 7) COSTA, Alessandra Mello; BARROS, Denise Franca; CARVALHO, José Luis Felício. *Adimensão histórica dos discursos acerca do empreendedor e do empreendedorismo*. Revista de Administração Contemporânea - RAC, Curitiba, v. 15, n. 2, art. 1, p.179-197, março-abril 2011.
- 8) CUNHA, Roberta Araújo Nascimento. *A universidade na formação de empreendedores: a percepção prática dos alunos de graduação*. In: Encontro Nacional da Associação Nacional de Pós-Graduação e Pesquisa em Administração, 28., 2004. Anais... Curitiba, PR, ANPAD, 2004. CD ROOM.
- 9) DOLABELA, Fernandes. *Pedagogia Empreendedora*. São Paulo: Editora de Cultura, 2003.
- 10) DOLABELA, Fernando. *O Segredo de Luísa*. São Paulo: Cultura, 1999.
- 11) DORNELAS, José Carlos Assis. *Empreendedorismo corporativo: como ser empreendedor, inovar e se diferenciar na sua empresa*. 6a ed., Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 2003.

- 12) DORNELAS, José Carlos Assis. *Empreendedorismo: transformando ideias em negócios*. 3aed., Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 2008.
- 13) DOUGLAS, Evan J.; FITZSIMMONS, Jason R. *Intrapreneurial intentions versus entrepreneurial intentions: distinct constructs with different antecedents*. *Small Bus Econ*, v.41, p.115-132, 2013.
- 14) DRUCKER, Peter Ferdinand. *Innovations and entrepreneurship: practice and principles*. New York: Harper&How, 1986.
- 15) ESTEVAM, Artilene Barros Rabelo. *Intra-Empreendedor e Dimensão Cultural: um estudo com trabalhadores de uma empresa cearense*. *Revista de Psicologia, Fortaleza*, v.3, n.1, p.94-109, janeiro-junho, 2012.
- 16) FERREIRA, Paulo Gitirana Gomes; MATTOS, Pedro Lincoln C. Leão. *Empreendedorismo e Práticas didáticas nos cursos de Graduação em Administração: os estudantes levantam o problema*. In: Encontro Nacional da Associação Nacional de Pós-Graduação, 27., 2003. Anais... Rio de Janeiro, RJ, ANPAD, 2003."
- 17) FILLION, Louis Jacques. *Empreendedorismo: empreendedores e proprietários-gerentes de pequenos negócios*. *Revista de Administração, São Paulo*, v.34, n.2, p.05-28, abril-junho 1999.
- 18) FILLION, Louis Jacques. *Entendendo os Intraempreendedores como visionistas*. *Revista de Negócios, Blumenau*, v.9, n.2, p.65-80, abril-junho, 2004.
- 19) GAWELL, Malin. *Social Entrepreneurship: Action Grounded in Needs, Opportunities and/or Perceived Necessities?* ISTR – International Society for Third Sector Research. v.24, p.1071-1090, 2013.
- 20) GEM – GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR. *Empreendedorismo no Brasil: Relatório Executivo*. 2012. Disponível em: <<http://www.gemconsortium.org/docs/download/221>>.
- 21) GIL, Antonio Carlos. *Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa*. São Paulo: Atlas, 2010.
- 22) LEITE, Elaine da Silveira. *O fenômeno do Empreendedorismo: criando riquezas*. Recife, Editora Bargaço, 2000.
- 23) LEITE, Elaine da Silveira; MELO, Natália Maximo. *Uma nova noção de empresário: a naturalização do "empreendedor"*. *Revista de Sociologia e Política, Curitiba*, v.16, n.31, p.35-47. 2008.
- 24) LIZOTE, Suzete Antonieta; et. al. *Comportamento Intraempreendedor: um estudo em instituições de ensino superior*. *Revista GUAL - Gestão Universitária na América Latina, Florianópolis*, v.6, n.1, p.233-252, janeiro, 2013.
- 25) LOPES, Rose (org). *Educação empreendedora: conceitos, modelos e práticas*. 1a ed., Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier; São Paulo: Sebrae, 2010.
- 26) MARKONI, Marina de Andrade; LAKATOS, Eva Maria. *Técnicas de Pesquisa*. São Paulo: Editora Atlas, 2008.
- 27) MARTENS, Cristina DaiPrá; FREITAS, Henrique. *Influência do ensino de empreendedorismo nas intenções de direcionamento profissional dos estudantes*. *Estudo & Debate, Lajeado*, v.15, p.71-95. 2008.
- 28) MARTES, Ana Cristina Braga. *Weber e Shumpeter: a ação econômica do empreendedor*. *Revista de Economia Política, São Paulo*, v.30, n.2, p.254-270, abril-junho. 2010."
- 29) MINAYO, M. C. S. (Org.). (2001). *Pesquisa social: teoria, método e criatividade*. Rio de Janeiro: Vozes.
- 30) PINCHOT III, Gifford. *Intrapreneuring – Why you don't have to leave the corporation to become*. 1a ed., New York: Harper & Row, 1985.

- 31) PREFEITURA DE RIBEIRÃO PRETO. Disponível em: <www.ribeiraopreto.sp.gov.br >. Acessado em: 02 de setembro de 2013.
- 32) REDFORD, Dana. *Entrepreneurship education in Portugal: 2004/2005 national survey*. Comportamento Organizacional e Gestão, Rio de Janeiro, v.12, n.1, p.19-41. 2006."
- 33) SANTOS, Susana Correia; CAETANO, Antonio; CURRAL, Luís. *Atitudes dos estudantes universitários face ao empreendedorismo*. Revista Portuguesa e Brasileira de Gestão, Lisboa, v.9, n.4, p.2-14, outubro-dezembro. 2010.
- 34) SCHMIDT, Serje; BOHNENBERGER, Maria Cristina. *Perfil empreendedor e Desempenho organizacional*. Revista de Administração Contemporânea, RAC, Curitiba, v.13, n.3, art.6, p.450-467, julho-agosto. 2009.
- 35) SEBRAE – Serviço Brasileiro de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas. Disponível em:<www.sebrae.com.br>. Acessado em 21 maio 2011.
- 36) SILVA, Marco Antonio Oliveria Monteiro; CORREIA, Manuela Faia; SCHOLTEN, Marc; GOMES, Luiz Flavio Autran Monteiro. *Cultura nacional e orientação empreendedora: um estudo comparativo entre Brasil e Portugal*. Comportamento Organizacional e Gestão, Riode Janeiro, v.14, n.1, p.65-84. 2008.
- 37) SOUZA, Eda Castro Lucas; GUIMARÃES, Tomás de Aquino (Organizadores). *Empreendedorismo além do plano do negócio*. São Paulo: Editora Atlas, 2005
- 38) YIN, Robert K. *Estudo de caso: planejamento e métodos*. 3a ed; Porto Alegre: Bookman, 2005.
- 39) ZOUAIN, Moraes Deborah; OLIVEIRA, Fátima Bayma; BARONE, Francisco Marcelo. *Construindo o perfil do jovem empreendedor brasileiro: relevância para a formulação e implementação de política de estímulo ao empreendedorismo*. Revista de Administração Pública, Rio de Janeiro, v.41, n.4, p.797-807, julho-agosto. 2007.